

MAIN ADVANTAGES AND OBSTACLES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE IN INDUSTRIAL COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT. Predictive maintenance is a highly effective and widely used approach to diagnosing machines, devices, and other equipment in a variety of industrial systems. A key feature is the use of data to predict when failures or malfunctions will occur. By collecting and analysing data from sensors and other technical means, algorithms in machine learning software can identify patterns that indicate when a component is expected to fail. This provides reliable information for managers to plan maintenance activities before failures occur, minimising downtime and interruptions to operations. This article reviews the definition of maintenance, types, and benefits of implementing predictive diagnostics. It is particularly useful for industrial machines and equipment, which often play a critical role in ensuring a continuous production process. The presence of unplanned downtime, process delays, or breakdowns often leads to significant losses in terms of productivity and profit. Implementing this approach helps to avoid these losses by ensuring that the equipment is always in optimal operating condition. Predictive diagnostics is one of the key innovations introduced by Industry 4.0. Thus, the analysis of data on critical operating parameters is often used in decision-making to optimise maintenance time, determine operating conditions, process engineering and re-engineering.

Key words: predictive maintenance, diagnostics, industry, competitive advantage.

ОСНОВНИ ПРЕДИМСТВА И ПРЕЧКИ ПРИ ВНЕДРЯВАНЕ НА ПРЕДСКАЗВАЩАТА ПОДДРЪЖКА В ПРОМИШЛЕНИТЕ КОМПАНИИ

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РЕЗЮМЕ. Предсказващата поддръжка е високоефективен и широко прилаган подход за диагностика на машини, апарати и друго оборудване в редица индустриални системи. Ключова характеристика е използването на данни, за да се предвиди времето за възникване на повреди или несъответствия. Чрез събиране и анализиране на данни от сензори и други технически средства, алгоритмите в даден софтуер, свързан с машинно обучение, могат да идентифицират модели, които показват кога се очаква даден компонент да се повреди. Това осигурява достоверна информация за мениджърите да планират дейности по поддръжка; преди възникване на повреди, с което минимизират времето за престои и прекъсване на операциите. Настоящата статия извършва преглед на определението за поддръжка, видовете поддръжка и ползите от внедряване на предсказваща диагностика. Тя е особено полезна за индустриални машини и оборудване, които често имат критична роля за осигуряване на непрекъснат производствен процес. Наличието на непланирани престои, забавяне на процеса или аварии често води до значителни загуби по отношение на производителност и печалба. Внедряването на този подход помага да се избегнат тези загуби, като осигурява гаранция, че оборудването винаги е в оптимално работно състояние. Предсказващата диагностика е една от ключовите иновации, въведени от индустрия 4.0. Така анализът на данни относно критични работни параметри често се използва при вземането на решения за оптимизиране на времето за поддръжка, определяне на работни състояния, инженеринг и реинженеринг на процеси.

Ключови думи: предсказваща поддръжка, диагностика, индустрия, конкурентно предимство.

Introduction

Predictive maintenance (PdM) is a strategic tool for diagnostics of industrial equipment, which is based on databases, aiming to avoid unplanned downtimes by predicting the optimal operating state of the monitored objects. This should avoid unnecessary replacement of spare parts and critical deviations in the quality of processes due to accidents or failures. This approach is one of the key innovations adopted by Industry 4.0. The implementation of continuous measurements and analysis of this maintenance allows managers to predict the remaining service life of machines and individual components with high accuracy. The definition of adequate critical operating parameters is often used as a decision-making tool for optimising downtime and determining the current operating state.

The implementation of observations on the operating characteristics of the equipment is based on a concept related to the application of monitoring techniques that register and collect information in real time about the operation of the monitored components. However, the use of this traditional approach does not allow for the prediction of related failures or wear. A turning point in this process was marked by the creation

of increasingly sophisticated sensors, more efficient and productive communication networks, and more powerful computer systems for processing data sets. This supports the process of comparing data with failure models using stochastic algorithms, which allows for the identification, simulation, and interpretation of different models with the registered operating parameters. The presence of these models that allows for more accurate calculation of forecasts regarding the operating life, as well as the unification of all operational data in the system into a single database. This leads to a real opportunity to optimise every aspect of the provision of services/products for the customer, but also for the supplier, who can implement improvements specific to their activity.

In today's turbulent environment, the availability of efficient and highly productive industrial facilities for the production of industrial products, mining, power, and resource sectors is a key component for progress and growth in developing economies. By implementing advanced predictive maintenance technologies, organisations and governments have the opportunity to perform fast and efficient diagnostics, which is essential for the aforementioned industries. Predictive maintenance not only extends the life of machines and industrial equipment, but also increases the safety and competitiveness

of an organisation. Preventing equipment failures means eliminating potentially dangerous incidents that could injure not only machine operators, but also people around them. On the other hand, this also achieves a high level of safe and healthy working conditions, which is part of the so-called social pillar in the concept of sustainable development. As a rule, in less developed regions, the equipment used in industry is older and therefore more susceptible to breakdowns and emergency situations. Any occurrence of a fault leads to a slowdown in production processes or even their shutdown, which threatens productivity and human health. For such regions, predictive maintenance, which provides information about when equipment needs repair or adjustment before it breaks down, is particularly important.

The application of this type of maintenance techniques in the working environment is often associated with improvements by installing new sensors in certain areas of machines, devices, vehicles and other long-lasting tangible assets. This provides a good opportunity to detect and solve problems with operating parameters before they cause a real emergency situation. If the data collected from the sensors show that the equipment's performance is deteriorating, there is a possibility of taking immediate repair actions. Known traditional maintenance methods include checking and adjusting at regular intervals, for example every three or six months. The presence of a failure can occur at any time, especially for continuous processes that are characterised by high intensity of wear and aging of parts and components. Therefore, obtaining data on the condition of the equipment continuously allows problems to be eliminated at the moment of their occurrence. By using techniques leading to early recognition of problems, the organisation can plan the maintenance of the machines and carry out any repairs or adjustments before the asset fails. The availability of such an approach has become a strong competitive advantage over the last decade, but it is necessary to overcome the economic barriers associated with processing a huge amount of data before concrete decisions for improvements can be made. The purpose of this study is to identify key advantages and main obstacles when implementing a predictive diagnostics system. The study will help to define leading elements in a comprehensive competitive strategy aimed at eliminating failures and accidents in the long term.

Equipment maintenance types

In modern industrial organisations, maintenance costs represent almost as large a percentage of operating costs as energy costs. However, there are still cases where this money is spent inefficiently by applying a reactive approach, which is associated with carrying out repairs after a failure has occurred. A number of managers who are engaged in maintenance of tangible assets are taking measures to more accurately predict the future condition of equipment in order to make adequate and more informed decisions in this direction.

According to studies by various authors, annual equipment maintenance costs vary widely, averaging up to 40% of total costs. For example, estimates of maintenance costs for manufacturing equipment range from 15% to 70% of the cost of manufactured products (Thomas and Weiss, 2018). Literature often uses different indicators and assessment methods, for example, Komonen (2002) estimates that industrial maintenance is 5.5% of the company's turnover (i.e. sales), but it varies from 0.5% to 25%. Other studies estimate that

maintenance is 37.5% of the total cost of ownership (Herrmann et al., 2011). Along with the variations in the indicators in the scientific literature on maintenance costs, the values vary depending on the country and industry of study, which makes comparison and generalisation difficult.

Therefore, in such a dynamic environment, the development of new technologies and effective maintenance strategies that can improve the performance and economic efficiency of equipment is essential. This has an important impact not only on the economic benefits of the equipment, but also on the reliability, availability, and security of the system. The development of maintenance technologies goes through three key stages: corrective maintenance, preventive maintenance, and predictive maintenance. Corrective maintenance is a “fault-only” approach, which is the initial stage of maintenance; preventive maintenance is carried out at predetermined intervals to check and replace parts, and to prevent damage, destruction and secondary losses; predictive maintenance is condition-based, and according to the condition of the system, it is decided whether to carry out repairs. Corrective maintenance and preventive maintenance are the traditional way of maintenance, which leads to lower equipment reliability and high maintenance costs. Predictive maintenance integrates equipment condition monitoring, fault diagnosis, adequate data for decision-making in predicting fault states and maintenance activities, which is a new way of thinking and can improve economic efficiency and reliability.

- *Corrective maintenance.* It is usually associated with practical activities to repair equipment when it breaks down or its performance deteriorates to levels that do not meet the set production goals. This is the so-called traditional approach to maintenance activities, which is accepted as a natural reaction to repair machines when they break down. The advantages of this approach in the short term are related to the seemingly low implementation costs. It is possible that the costs per month are equal to what is needed to repair a damaged machine, or even lower if an emergency situation does not occur. Secondly, a minimum number of maintenance personnel is needed, since the machines are repaired by operators who are familiar with their technical parameters. This approach can be successfully applied when all the equipment is new, since a high degree of reliability and good performance are realistically expected and achievable at the beginning of the life cycle.

In the opposite direction are a number of weaknesses associated with this maintenance approach. Some of the most commonly identified are: increased operating costs over a long period of time due to unplanned equipment downtime; increased labour costs, especially if an emergency repair is required; urgent costs for emergency repairs or replacement of critical components; possible damage to non-productive machines or processes due to the shutdown of essential ones; reduced motivation among people due to stress in the workplace. In most work situations, these disadvantages are the opposite of the possible benefits. For example, adopting a program to reduce monthly maintenance costs for a heating installation is likely to be ineffective if it breaks down in bad weather conditions in winter. Productivity can be severely reduced if it is too cold to open the work premises. Managers are forced to wait for maintenance personnel to carry out the necessary repairs. This can lead to the second point - increased labour costs. The urgency and specificity of the equipment may require calling in outside help or paying staff overtime to work overtime. And if managers decide not to make this expenditure, it must wait until

the building is habitable again. Either way, this scenario significantly increases maintenance costs. Therefore, although corrective maintenance is easy to plan, its widespread implementation can lead to production shutdowns when key machines fail. Thus, without immediate access to the necessary components, the costs of emergency delivery along the supply chain can increase dramatically. In essence, the lack of a strategy for implementing this approach can lead to increased downtime and higher maintenance costs.

- *Preventive maintenance*. This approach refers to the regular maintenance of equipment according to a predetermined schedule, which is based on the characteristics and individual features of the equipment, usually provided by its manufacturer. The main goal here is to extend the life of tangible assets, as well as to prevent potential failures. Typically, a preventive maintenance program includes periodically scheduled activities, such as replacing moving parts and filters, cleaning internal and external coils, lubricating motors and bearings, cleaning and disinfecting cooling towers, adjusting and checking control modules, painting and controlling corrosion processes.

The implementation of preventive maintenance has a number of advantages in ensuring the reliability and performance of equipment compared to corrective maintenance. Therefore, it is associated with lower costs over a long period of time, as it reduces emergency situations and unplanned outages. Studies in this direction show that 12-18% of costs can be reduced when implementing preventive maintenance compared to corrective maintenance. (Sullivan et al., 2010)

A significant disadvantage of preventive maintenance in a highly dynamic economic environment is the lack of the ability to clearly prioritise. In other words, equipment is evaluated in the same way and maintenance is performed according to a pre-established schedule with recommended activities. There is often no reasonable system for classifying maintenance activities according to the potential consequences of failure, so people do not necessarily pay primary attention to key tangible assets. For example, changing a filter in an air conditioning system for a drone test would have the same weight as replacing a temperature sensor in a fire protection system. The former is likely to have minimal impact on the flight characteristics of the aircraft, while the failure of the latter could be catastrophic, especially for facilities with a high degree of cargo hazard. By performing preventive maintenance as the equipment designer intended, we will increase reliability closer to the design level. The “checklist” approach to preventive maintenance is better than the corrective “wait-for-it-to-fail” approach, but is less effective and efficient than the optimal approach - predictive maintenance.

- *Predictive maintenance*. Like preventive maintenance, predictive maintenance is based on the principle that a proactive approach is better than a corrective one. In return, however, repairs are not carried out based on a pre-established calendar schedule, but on an assessment of the actual operating condition of the equipment. Thus, key operating parameters are checked and data from them is recorded continuously by personnel or by sensors. The readings are then analysed and used to assess the condition of the equipment and predict future performance or the probability of failure. These measurements indicate the beginning of deterioration of operating parameters (functional condition), thus eliminating or controlling the causes before significant deterioration of the physical condition of the tangible asset. A key element of predictive maintenance is that the current condition of the equipment and the production

system determines the direction of the activities performed, rather than adhering to a pre-established schedule. This means that repairs are made at the right time, resources are not wasted on unnecessary work, and equipment is maintained at a higher level of performance and reliability. On the other hand, this approach reduces costs by an additional 8-12% overall compared to preventive maintenance. (Sullivan et al., 2010)

Predictive maintenance activities should be prioritised within the organisation based on the organisation's unique characteristics and the skills and knowledge of the people involved. In some cases, significant investment in training or new employees with specific competencies may be required. A production testing facility will need sufficient staff with technical expertise to continuously monitor and trend all data coming from the sensors in place and compare this information to the optimal performance metrics provided by each manufacturer. Maintenance should then be prioritised based on the potential impact on costs, ergonomics, and safety. It is important to note that additional staff will likely be needed to actually go out and fix the problems found.

The implementation of predictive maintenance is often hindered by one key drawback, and that is the necessary costs that the organisation must foresee. Additional financial resources may be required to implement and maintain new software solutions that collect and process data on the current state of the equipment in use. Operators will likely need to undergo additional training, and people with specific knowledge and skills in the field will also need to be attracted. Regardless of whether these activities are in-house or outsourced, performing analysis and prioritisation leads to increased investments in this direction. The scope of the mentioned factors will depend largely on the scale and globalisation of the production systems and the adopted organisational culture. Therefore, the implementation of this approach represents a serious challenge for a number of organisations, as it requires commitment and approval from senior management. The biggest obstacle stands out the need to change the organisational culture, which is the driving force for implementing the planned improvements.

Advantages and obstacles of implementing predictive maintenance as a diagnostic tool

In a highly competitive environment, modern supply chains are becoming increasingly complex and unpredictable, making them more vulnerable to disruptions in their rhythm. That is why managers, responding to these transformations, are looking for opportunities for reliable and sustainable production processes over time with minimal delays or interruptions. In response to this need, predictive maintenance has emerged as a critical area of research in the management of various industrial systems. The leading goal of the strategic predictive maintenance approach is to prevent unforeseen equipment failures, while increasing productivity and minimising the costs and downtime they cause. Various software solutions based on the so-called precedent method can identify deviations, and through data analysis to predict possible upcoming emergency conditions. Thus, the capabilities for proactive planning and execution of maintenance tasks enable people to reduce unplanned downtime to improve the overall efficiency of the organization. (Schwendemann et al., 2021). Other conventional approaches, such as corrective and preventive maintenance, are often associated with the need for premature replacement of spare

parts or the occurrence of unplanned outages. Therefore, long downtimes or high costs for preventive activities and spare parts are possible. The implementation of condition-based maintenance (CBM) successfully overcomes these problems because it constantly monitors the current operating characteristics of the maintenance objects. However, predictive diagnostics extends this approach by calculating and analysing the remaining optimal condition, which allows for a preliminary selection of the necessary maintenance measures and replacement of spare parts before failure. As a result, a number of failures can be avoided at an early stage, which is especially useful in interconnected and continuous industrial processes with bottlenecks and expensive spare parts. Thus, indirect maintenance costs that are alternative due to the occurrence of a failure can actually be minimised. (Busse et al., 2019).

Despite the undeniable advantages and recognised potential of predictive maintenance to increase operational efficiency and reduce downtime and breakdowns, the number of successful implementations in industrial organisations remains disproportionately low compared to other approaches. One of the representative studies in this direction shows that 60% of the surveyed organisations in Europe have an adopted strategic goal to introduce the approach, but only 11% have successfully completed this task. (Haarman et al., 2018). Such studies provide real information about the different options for planning and practical implementation of strategic goals and tasks. The presented literature data provides information about successful examples related to effective maintenance management and sustainable production processes without unplanned failures. However, they lack clearly expressed consistently repeated effective implementations in industrial organisations that would exceed the theoretically presented possibilities. (Srivastava and Mondal, 2016; Welte et al., 2020). To clarify the reasons for the low rate of practical applications and to develop models in this direction, it is necessary to summarise successful solutions and classify them by economic sectors. Some authors examine various economic models that are based on artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, case base **reasoning** and other empirical data in the field. (Passlick et al., 2021). In line with this are the studies of van Oudenhoven et al. (2022) for more practically oriented research in the field of predictive maintenance implementation. In their observations on the implementation of predictive maintenance, Hoffmann and Lasch (2023) emphasise the need for empirical records that explain in more detail the reasons for the small number of successful applications, and analyse the critical factors for implementation.

- Obstacles to implementing predictive maintenance

The implementation of a successful predictive maintenance system in industrial organisations is associated with overcoming numerous obstacles and complications, which are generally accepted as significant shortcomings in the future. The huge amounts of data required to actually implement the approach must be adequately collected and analysed, which is a significant problem. Managers have difficulty deciding on the investment in infrastructure and other resources required to effectively process, manage, and evaluate this data. The introduction of information from multiple sources, such as sensors, logs for condition assessment, has the potential to create confusion among people in making the optimal decision.

The need for more people with good professional training in data processing and analysis and machine learning is also a critical problem for the approach. The organisation may not have people with specific experience and abilities needed to

implement a predictive maintenance system. Hiring new people, training existing ones, or contracting with external consultants often takes a lot of time and additional financial resources. In addition, building a comprehensive management system aimed at this approach is likely to face data unification due to the complexity and individual characteristics of the various machines and equipment used. They may require different methods and algorithms for unifying data from installed software solutions. Internal resistance and lack of leadership skills among senior management is another serious problem in adopting the necessary changes. The absence of support and internal motivation for adopting such an innovative approach can be identified in people who prefer conventional methods of corrective and preventive maintenance. That is why it is extremely important that senior management and people be informed about the key benefits of predictive maintenance and how it can increase overall productivity and efficiency.

The main obstacles to implementing a predictive maintenance system in the context of Industry 4.0 are examined in detail and analysed as challenges and opportunities by Nunes et al. (2023). Key issues are investigated, such as: guidelines for real-time data analysis, merging data from different sources and formats, creating and offering predictive models based on precedents in complex industrial systems, etc. The authors also describe a set of proposals and possible solutions to the above-mentioned problems related to improving reliability and productivity. Some of the most common challenges are related to complicated access to accurate and reliable data on the operating condition of the equipment; inadequate data collection and analysis, as they are often scattered across different software platforms in different formats; high investments for the acquisition and installation of sensors, devices, software, and system upgrades. (Filipov and Vasilev, 2016)

Developing a predictive maintenance system for industrial equipment using algorithms related to the precedent method is practically feasible in a short period of time and without high additional investments. Using this approach would enable organisations to predict possible failures and solutions accurately and efficiently. This will lead to increased operational efficiency, reduced maintenance costs, increased customer satisfaction, and a strong competitive advantage. Systematising the following advantages are critical factors for the potential successful implementation of a comprehensive predictive diagnostics strategy.

- Post-implementation benefits of predictive maintenance

It should be emphasised that the perception of predictive maintenance as a competitive advantage it is not a universal solution. Successful implementation is associated with the assessment of individual features, customisation, modification, and development of almost every operation. Thus, the benefits are primarily related to: minimising the risk of unexpected failures and extending the life of assets; reducing maintenance costs by avoiding unnecessary repairs; optimising the availability of spare parts; and maximising reliability.

The advantages regarding the implemented production processes are related to ensuring high reliability by eliminating serious failures that compromise the planned rhythm. In a continuous production cycle, it is extremely important that the equipment can operate with optimal characteristics even during maintenance activities. This is a key objective in a number of strategic plans. Reliability is evaluated primarily by the mean time to repair, deviation response time, and availability of resources for troubleshooting. Through the predictive

diagnostics approach, many possible failures can be predicted in advance, preparing and planning the necessary maintenance measures. In addition, unplanned downtime can affect subsequent process steps, leading to interruptions and large losses, especially in assembly line workshops.

Compared to other maintenance approaches where the current condition of the facility is unknown, such as corrective or time-based maintenance, predictive maintenance enables the prevention of unplanned downtime. Therefore, response time is minimised; there is a practical opportunity to secure resources and reduce mean time to repair, as maintenance personnel are effectively prepared for the next restoration of operational status. This effectively prepares for upcoming maintenance activities during non-production time, setup time, or when equipment is moved to another department.

One of the key advantages of predictive maintenance is that it can be considered as an extension of condition-based maintenance as it involves *continuous monitoring* of diagnostic objects. Therefore, sudden failures can be identified because the system provides 24/7 monitoring of the objects, especially in continuous processes where stopping and starting production is expensive and energy-intensive. This, in turn, ensures stable operation of the equipment, which is of great importance for interconnected and environmentally critical processes. When failures or accidents occur, errors can affect product quality and lead to failure or scrap. In addition, the constantly known condition of the maintenance objects also has a positive impact on risk management. In particular, processes without critical equipment carry a high risk of downtime throughout the entire production chain, which can be mitigated by an appropriate data-driven maintenance strategy. The large amount of data allows for easy identification of the condition of the equipment based on information from multiple sensors. These quantitative parameters can be used for graphical presentation, which provides a good overview of the condition of all maintenance objects.

The ability to accurately predict the remaining useful life of equipment allows one to predict when an emergency will occur, which helps managers plan the necessary maintenance measures in advance. The main elements here are: financial resources, people, spare parts, and tools. In time-based preventive maintenance, planning the necessary measures is relatively easy, since the intervals are fixed. However, this strategy carries the risk of unplanned failures and emergencies. In comparison, predictive diagnostics can detect failures in advance with enough time to plan resources, making it suitable for automating repair processes using artificial intelligence.

Legal regulations and corporate measures to improve *health and safety* at work are constantly increasing, along with reliability and cost-effectiveness. Health and environmental protection are linked to two main directions. One is aimed at ensuring that no harmful substances are released into the environment by continuously monitoring facilities with hazardous substances and detecting leaks at an early stage of the process. On the other hand, predictive maintenance has additional positive environmental effects, as fewer spare parts have to be produced and transported, and less waste is produced due to the optimal use of wear opportunities.

Continuous monitoring and maintaining optimal parameters allows for extensive root cause analysis in the event of failures. On the one hand, such data from operating time to failure is very valuable for training and optimising algorithms for remaining useful life. On the other hand, it can be used to create a

knowledge database for maintenance personnel, including failure indicators and their causes. Such a database is also used to categorise and visualise defects. In this way, it is possible to monitor both critical points and key causes of errors, and to implement strategically prioritised improvement measures.

To assess the impact of predictive maintenance on costs, it is necessary to divide them into direct and indirect costs.

Direct costs include all those related to the maintenance measures actually carried out, such as spare parts, human resources, and additional materials. Long-term benefits from the reduction of manual labour and the associated savings in operational maintenance are often added here. Compared to time-based preventive maintenance, predictive maintenance results in fewer measures, as the wear reserve is fully used and parts are replaced less frequently, which leads to reduced material costs. In addition, predictive maintenance requires fewer people on hand, as the risks of unplanned breakdowns and accidents are minimal. Since spare parts can be delivered on demand and less inventory needs to be maintained, storage costs are also reduced.

Indirect maintenance costs are opportunity costs that arise due to failures. Especially in manufacturing organisations where very short technological time intervals have to be maintained, individual system failures can lead to expensive scrap and reduced productivity, which leads to reduced profits. Therefore, accurate prediction of the condition of critical equipment is beneficial in avoiding high subsequent costs. Furthermore, production interruptions can lead to non-fulfillment of agreed deliveries along the logistics chain. As a result, customers are likely to resort to very high contractual penalties. To avoid such events in the event of a failure, expensive *ad-hoc* measures are required. Predictive maintenance thus gains a significant advantage by *extending the life of the equipment* by reducing or eliminating breakdowns and failures by replacing only worn-out spare parts. Furthermore, expensive replacement investments can be reduced and the life cycle costs of the equipment can decrease significantly over time.

Effective implementation of predictive maintenance provides significant strategic advantages for the organisational structure and competitiveness of organisations. Continuous monitoring and forecasting of operating conditions can limit reductions or overproduction in critical production processes, allowing for a *more efficient organisation of units (departments)* with less unused capacity. By more efficiently using existing capacities, all other things being equal, higher productivity is achieved based on optimised availability, while reducing production areas. Similar results are often complemented by activities related to supply chain management. Predictive maintenance associated with reducing the risk of unplanned interruptions and downtime means that fewer spare parts need to be stored. This provides more space for *high-value production activities*. These savings have a positive environmental impact, as continuous condition monitoring also detects worn components and unusual interruptions, *preventing excessive energy consumption*.

Adopting a predictive maintenance approach always involves the use of data collection methods based on sensors and other sensitive elements. The huge amount of data in volume and scope can be used as a strategic tool by equipment manufacturers to optimise future versions of machines and to identify weaknesses based on the *collected baseline information*. In addition, there is the advantage of being able to *customise sales opportunities* to customer wishes, such as

modules with case studies that are individually adapted and take into account the condition of the machine and operating conditions.

Many industrial organisations are well aware of the critical impact of product cost on competitiveness over the *life cycle* phases. Predictive maintenance under certain conditions leads to a reduction in operating costs, which is an opportunity for manufacturers and suppliers in the supply chain to generate competitive advantage through *differentiation* in a turbulent environment. Thus, customers in the chain include life cycle costs in negotiations for new equipment and contractually reserve the right to renegotiate prices after a few years if the planned costs for this are not achieved.

Conclusion

In a highly competitive and challenging economic environment, organisations must overcome a number of obstacles and hurdles before building a predictive maintenance system, including data administration, a shortage of experienced people, complex technologies, and resistance to change. After the successful implementation and adoption of the predictive maintenance approach, there are significant benefits for organisations related to reducing maintenance costs, reducing downtime, and increasing overall productivity and efficiency. The described difficulties and advantages of implementing predictive maintenance are intended to assist managers in creating and implementing a comprehensive strategy that generates added value for all stakeholders.

Predictive maintenance should be seen as a long-term investment in the sustainable implementation of production processes. The financial benefits are unlikely to be visible in the short term, but by preventing accidents and indirect maintenance costs in critical processes, they would become clear. Predictive maintenance is therefore an essential element of the overall strategy of any industrial organisation that leads to the reduction of risks to stability, health and safety of people and the environment.

From another perspective, predictive maintenance is not a solution to all problems related to optimising production processes. Therefore, it is advisable to apply it purposefully to critical systems, where failures must be prevented due to safety concerns, operational sustainability or the occurrence of indirect maintenance costs. The approach itself could not achieve high efficiency as a stand-alone solution and requires complete integration into the organisation. The implementation is often hindered by inadequate information infrastructure and a shortage of programmers and artificial intelligence specialists. These are all needed to connect with existing application systems and meet the requirements of the organisation and its customers. These problems are not unique and are common obstacles for many technologies in the Internet of Things environment. In addition, the reluctance of many employees to adopt new technologies is a major problem in practice. This problem is also evident in the challenge of implementing top-down approaches when employees do not accept them. One solution is to provide comprehensive information to dispel prejudices and demonstrate the benefits for all people involved in the process.

Modern predictive maintenance tools can achieve incredible results, especially when people combine sensors with a top-notch software system. Together, these tools can predict

machine failures before they happen and issue alerts, so that maintenance teams know exactly where they are needed. Such systems could even generate work orders and schedule tasks automatically, so that maintenance teams never miss a beat. The future promises to deliver even more. Artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies are poised to enhance diagnostic capabilities, so that they can identify the root causes of machine failures and recommend solutions. Operations that successfully implement the best of today's tools will be well-positioned for the technologies of tomorrow.

Adopting a predictive maintenance pilot program allows organisations to test and refine their strategies, thereby ensuring the success of the improvements undertaken before they are discovered by competitors. Continuous monitoring and data analysis are crucial for identifying potential equipment failures and effectively prioritising maintenance tasks.

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